

Short-term electricity consumption forecasting with NARX, LSTM, and SVR for a single building: small data set approach

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Nowadays, there is an undoubted change of trend towards a decentralized and decarbonised electric grid, where the electric generation based on local resources will take on special relevance. In this context, the encouragement of collective self-consumption (CSC) becomes one of the key issues. One of the aspects that will contribute to this aim is the development of power consumption-forecasting tools. This article proposes the comparison of three models to perform a day ahead consumption forecasting of ESTIA 2 building: nonlinear autoregressive neural network with exogenous inputs (NARX), long-short-term memory cell (LSTM) and support vector regression (SVR). First, the models structure has been designed by selecting the suitable-input combination and the optimal time window (TW) for the three models. Then, parameters of each model have been adjusted to achieve the most accurate prediction. After forecasting separately winter and summer seasons, experiments reveal that the proposed NARX neural network is the one that predicts with the highest accuracy in both winter and summer months, obtaining a mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) of 14,1% and 12% respectively. Likewise, regardless of the model, better results have been obtained in summer predictions, which is closely related to the dependence of the building's consumption on the heating, ventilation and air conditioning (HVAC) system.

Keywords: Collective self-consumption; Artificial Neural Networks; Nonlinear Autoregressive Exogenous; Long-Short-Term Memory Cell; Support Vector Regression.

Introduction

The digitalisation and decentralisation of the electric grid, as well as self-consumption, have become key elements to integrate more renewable energy in the nowadays-electric grid. In addition, taking into consideration a context where the global energy consumption, and in particular electricity consumption, is steadily rising, the management of energy generation and consumption has assumed particular importance.

The following work has been developed within the EKATE project, a POCTEFA project that seeks to respond to the above mentioned challenges focusing on encouraging collective self-consumption (CSC) of photovoltaic (PV) energy. EKATE's pilot project located in Izarbel Technology Park (Bidart, Frane) is the starting point for the analysis carried out in this work.

Europe has taken steps forward establishing legislative frameworks aimed at keeping the European Union (EU) in the position of the global leader in renewable energy. The revised Renewable Energy Directive (REDII) is one of the evidences of their strong commitment. Whereas individual self-consumption approach is allowed in almost all European countries, REDII introduces the basic definitions and requirement of CSC and energy communities (ECs) [1].

Being buildings responsible of 40% of energy consumption in the EU [2], there is much to be done reducing the electricity needs of buildings, as well as improving

their energy efficiency. In addition, given the possibilities that buildings offer for the installation of PV arrays, especially in their roofs, a significant amount of energy could be generated in buildings.

For facilitating the implementation of CSC in buildings, effective energy management systems (EMSs) need to be developed. One of the technical objectives established in EKATE is the design of an EMS that should lead to an increase of the self-consumption ratio and to the improvement of the building energy efficiency. To this end, the prediction of energy consumption and production of a building has been performed.

So far, different techniques have been applied for prediction purposes. Taking into consideration that the prediction technique needs to be able to manage time series data, the focus should be on the most relevant time series models. Among these models, on the one hand, we find statistical models as auto-regressive moving average (ARMA), auto-regressive integrated moving average (ARIMA) and other variations of both models, which include exogenous inputs, auto-regressive integrated moving average with exogenous input (ARIMAX) or support the modelling of the seasonal component, seasonal auto-regressive integrated moving average (SARIMA) [3]. On the other hand, there are techniques widely applied in the last years for energy prediction purposes: artificial neural networks (ANNs) [4] and other artificial intelligence (AI) methods, as support vector machines (SVM). Much work has been done in different fields making comparison of those traditional techniques (ARMA, ARIMAX, SARIMA...) and new ANN [5]. ARIMA based models, for example, can present problems in many complex systems related to non-linearity and even non-stationarity of the analysed time series [6].

ANNs have been used for different prediction purposes. In [7], a long short-term memory (LSTM), together with other data-driven approaches has been applied to perform one-hour step forecast of the energy production of a 1.15 MW PV power plant. The comparison of the forecasting performance of a traditional ARMAX technique and a nonlinear auto-regressive neural network with exogenous inputs (NARX) is conducted in [8]. In this study, the New England electrical load data are used to train and validate both models, effectively concluding that the second one forecasts with higher accuracy.

Paying now more attention to buildings, different methods have been used to predict the heat power of a building. Thus, [9] devises a method where in addition to the outdoor meteorological parameters, the accuracy of the prediction is considerably increased by taking into account as inputs the users behaviour factor, as well as the indoor temperature. In the case of ANNs for building electricity consumption forecasting, LSTMs and convolutional neural networks (CNNs) have been widely applied due to their performance in accurately modelling both short and long-term dependencies in data [10]. In [11], a ϵ -SVM regression based on a radial basis function (RBF) and NARX are compared through the performance of both, forecasting building consumption at the district scale. The conclusions point to a significant performance improvement with NARX compared to support vector regression (SVR).

Most papers tend to avoid the complexity of predicting the consumption of a single building by forecasting the electricity consumption of a group of buildings.

Anyway, some articles forecast individual building power consumption. In [12], the electricity and gas consumption, as well as the consumption related to the air conditioning system of a single building are forecasted using nine different ANNs. In this study, a 4-year dataset was used, of which 80% was used for training and 20% for validation. Better results are obtained in the prediction of both, electricity and gas consumption, than in the prediction of air conditioning consumption, the latter being somewhat less accurate due to the random nature of air conditioning use. In [13], LSTM and SVR models are used to perform, on the one hand, day-ahead power consumption forecasting and, on the other hand, peak and off-peak consumption forecasting. A large dataset is used for prediction (5 years for training and 1 year for validation). It is concluded that LSTM suits better when forecasting with enough data for training while SVR is more appropriate when less data is used for training.

Thus, it is worth mentioning that most case studies in the literature rely on large datasets when making predictions. However, there are cases where, for example due to the fact that the building is new, few data are available and therefore the model has to be trained with a small data set. Some studies as in [14] show that methods such as multi-distribution mega-trend diffusion (MD-MTD) to augment the small dataset can be effective in solving the problem of limited data availability in the case of wind energy prediction. In [15] a single building consumption forecasting is performed using a small dataset. It is shown that both, auto-regressive exogenous (ARX) and NARX models performs satisfactory. Even so, in the literature, it is difficult to find case studies in which a small dataset has to be used to make predictions, and even more so, to predict using ANN.

Regarding the analysis of the inputs used for the forecasting of electricity consumption of a building, in most cases the model is trained using historical meteorological data. However, in order to understand the building behaviour, it is sometimes not sufficient to consider only outdoor weather data. In [16], an input that considers the difference between workdays and weekends is used in order to forecast the consumption of a building using LSTM. [13] also considers two short-term load forecasting techniques, LSTM and SVR, taking as inputs weather variables, including wind speed, outdoor temperature, and relative humidity, together with the a binary array that differentiates workdays and non-workdays. In [17], a hybrid prediction model based on machine learning is proposed for the daily prediction of the heating and cooling demand of a building. To improve its prediction accuracy, several internet of things (IoT) sensors are implemented to read temperatures, building operation schedules (mainly occupancy) and outdoor weather data. In [18], the cooling energy prediction in summer for a hotel building located in southern Poland is carried out using both, ANN and SVR. In this case, meteorological data, a time array and the occupancy level are considered as inputs.

In the literature review, it has been found that the prediction of building power consumption is widely studied and that the use of ANN to make such predictions is widely applied. [19] offers a review of fifty papers that develop data-driven models for building scale application. Moreover, this study includes a count of the number of studies applying the different building energy consumption modelling and forecasting

techniques reviewed. It can be clearly seen how the study of ANN-based techniques for the prediction of building energy consumption has gained much interest in recent years in contrast to other techniques such as statistical regression or autoregressive models.

LSTMs and recurrent neural networks (RNNs) are widely applied in several research studies, together with hybrid models: CNN-LSTM, Deep RNN-LSTM. In [20], a comparison between LSTM, conventional ANN and SVR techniques is conducted when carrying out the forecast of energy use of 5 building groups, using 4 years length data, concluding that best prediction accuracy is obtained by using the designed LSTM. Although there are many studies that make comparisons between different machine learning (ML) techniques, there are hardly any studies in the literature that analyse cases where it is difficult to obtain usable and representative data, whereas this difficulty is very common in real cases.

In this paper, NARX, LSTM and SVR forecasters are used to predict the day-ahead hourly electricity consumption of a single building using a small training data set. There are three reasons why it has been chosen to use a small training dataset:

- ESTIA 2 smart meter was activated at the end of 2019. In addition, due to the pandemic situation, the building power consumption is not representative during some certain periods.
- The use of little data to train the prediction models allows the models to be updated often, due to the low computational demand. Thus, unlike models trained once with several years of data, our models are able to take into account changes in building consumption due to unexpected modifications, such as the use of new high-consumption electrical appliances in the building.
- When a new building joins a CSC entity, a large data set of its consumption is often not available. The small training dataset approach allows new buildings to be included in the EMS quickly.

The objective of our research work is to compare, for different seasons, the prediction accuracy of the three above-mentioned predictors trained with a small data set, in a setting where the building heating ventilation and air conditioning (HVAC) operation is highly stochastic.

These are the contributions of this research study:

- The comparison of forecasting results of the above mentioned three ML different forecasters.
- The use of a small training data set to carry out the prediction of the building electricity consumption.
- The use of occupancy signal as an input of the forecasters. A comparison between the use of this occupancy curve and a classical binary array that differentiates work days and weekends/holydays.
- The analysis of the influence of the stochastic use of HVAC appliance in the electricity consumption forecast considering winter and summer predictions.

This paper is organised as follows. In the second section, the studied case and the used data are presented. The proposed methodology is described in the next section. Then,

the design of the forecasters is given step by step in the fourth section. A discussion on the obtained results is carried out in the fifth section. Finally, conclusions are gathered in the last section.

Case study

ESTIA 2 building description

ESTIA 2 building is located in Izarbel technological park (Bidart, France). It has four floors. It is one of the three buildings of ESTIA Institute of Technology included in the studied CSC application. Different types of users of ESTIA 2 can be distinguished: teachers-researchers, students and workers of start-ups. These people use offices, laboratories, classrooms, toilets, meeting rooms and a dining room. Taking into consideration the different schedules and usage of each type of user, the electricity consumption of the building varies significantly throughout the year.

In terms of electrical loads, the HVAC system consumes the most. It consists of 10 outdoor heat pumps and about 73 indoor units. Each unit supplies several rooms with heat or cold by means of a heat transfer fluid and fans.

Figure 1. Top view of the building ESTIA 2 building.

Data description

The three prediction models studied in this work are based on data. Different types of data have been considered as possible inputs for the model.

The historical power consumption data (P_b) is crucial for models training. This data has been provided by the Linky smart meter of ESTIA 2 building with a time step of 10 minutes.

An important factor affecting the quality and reliability of these data is the COVID-19 pandemic lockout. Indeed, from mid-March to the end of May and from the end of October to the end of the year, most of the people who usually work in ESTIA 2 have had to work remotely.

Figure 2. ESTIA 2 building load profile of 2020.

Regarding the identification of outliers, the first deficiency in load registration occurs during the afternoon and night of 20th of February, when the load drops dramatically under 6kW. In addition, other two cases must also be highlighted in 15th and 26th of February in which the consumption drops suddenly to 0kW. Linear interpolation has been used to solve the problem of these outliers.

The data set has been decomposed and normalised in order to meet the forecasting modelling method requirements. Due to the non-conventional measures obtained because of the different periods of lockdown, winter and summer month's data has been selected for the analysis.

As mentioned above, load is registered with a 10 minutes time step while prediction is carried out for each hour of the next day. Therefore, as the next step of the data pre-processing, the hourly mean value of the load has been calculated. As a final step, the normalisation of data in the range [0,1] has been carried out. This is crucial for the design and tuning steps of some prediction models, because using normalized data, saturation of the neurons is avoided.

Due to the influence that weather has on the building consumption, external ambient temperature (T_a) and irradiance (R) have been considered as possible inputs. Data measured for the whole year 2020 for both variables have been obtained from Biarritz airport meteorological station located more or less 3 km far from ESTIA 2, with an hourly time step.

In addition to meteorological variables, possible inputs related to the use of the building have been also taken into account. On the one hand, a classical binary array (*bin*) that differentiates between working days ('1') and weekends ('0') has been created. On the other hand, thanks to information related to the schedules of the users of ESTIA 2 obtained from ESTIA engineering faculty, a daily curve of the building average occupancy during workdays, a work day occupancy curve (*OCC*), has been built (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. ESTIA 2 building daily occupancy curve.

Forecasters design methodology

In this section the forecasters design methodology is described. Figure 4 shows the different steps of the applied methodology.

Figure 4. Different steps of the forecasters design methodology.

Input selection

Among the above-mentioned four possible inputs (T_a , R , bin and OCC), it is necessary to select those that best characterize the building consumption behaviour. Therefore, a correlation analysis has been carried out in order to bring out which above-mentioned variables are most correlated with the building consumption. For that purpose, Pearson correlation coefficient is used:

$$r = \frac{\sum(x-\bar{x})(y-\bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum(x-\bar{x})^2(y-\bar{y})^2}} \quad (1)$$

where x and y are two different variables and \bar{x} and \bar{y} are the mean values of both.

The correlation coefficient, r , is a measure of the linear correlation between two sets of data. It ranges from -1 to 1. A positive correlation means that when one of the variables increases the other one also increases. Whereas a negative or inverse

correlation indicates that when a variables increases the other one decreases. A correlation is considered strong when the Pearson coefficient has an absolute value higher than 0.5.

Correlation analysis has been made in both, winter and summer months. In addition, weekends have not been taken into consideration due to the lack of relevance that these days have to see how the possible input variables affect the power consumption of the building.

In addition to the correlation study, another analysis has been carried out for the selection of the models inputs. It consisted of comparing the mean absolute percentage error (MAPE, see Eq. (2)) obtained by introducing different combinations of inputs to each model.

Forecaster models

ANN

One of the principle reason why this method has become so popular lies in its capability to represent non-linear and, in general, complex systems.

Main units of an ANN are neurons. In addition, three types of layers compose ANN: input layer, hidden layer and output layer. Each layer has a certain number of neurons, which will be connected by means of adjustable weights. ANN are trained by learning algorithms. During this learning process, initial weights are modified in order to minimize the cost function of the network [21].

RNNs are nowadays one of the most frequently used ANNs and are characterized by their capability to process several non-linear dynamic system thanks to their internal connections.

Nonlinear Autoregressive Exogenous Neural Network

NARX are a type of RNN that differs from typical LSTM or gated recurrent unit (GRU) networks especially in terms of architecture and learning procedure [6]. NARX has recurrent dynamic architectures and differently from other RNNs, the recurrence is given only by the feedback of the output [6]. By contrast, in other types of RNNs the recurrence is given by the entire internal state of the network.

The network is trained in open-loop using the historical values of the output. During testing process, it is used in close-loop by feeding back each predicted load value to perform the next 24h forecast.

Figure 5 shows the general scheme of a regular NARX network, in operational mode:

Figure 5. Close-loop architecture of a NARX network [6]

where x and y represent the input and outputs respectively, W_i^{h1} is the weight matrix, b_{hi} is the bias and finally the TDL block represents the tapped-delay lines.

Long Short-Term Neural Network

In RNNs output vector returns to the input after a time delay. This enables simple RNN with a short-term memory. However, in the case of longer-term dependencies, RNNs tend to suffer from the very common problem of vanishing or exploding gradients [22, 23]. That was the main motivation behind the growth of LSTM, which have the capacity to learn large data. According to the literature, LSTMs have a good behaviour forecasting time sequences.

Each layer of LSTM is composed of several memory cells, also called LSTM cells. The structure of the cell constitutes of some ‘gates’. The input gate add new data, the forget gate delete unnecessary data, the cell state has the long-term memory and finally, the output gate transmits data to the next cell.

In the case of this study, only one LSTM hidden layer composed of several cells is included.

Super Vector Regression

Vapnik's ϵ -tube support vector regression (ϵ -SVR) is the common formulation of SVR [24]. Suppose we are given a training data set $(x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2), \dots, (x_n, y_n)$, where n is the total number of training samples, in ϵ -SVR the goal is to find a linear relationship between input and target, $f(x)$, that has at most ϵ deviation from the targets y_i for all the training data [6]. Sometimes, however, this may not be the case and slack variables can be introduced to capture residuals beyond the ϵ boundary to cope with otherwise infeasible constraints of the optimization problem.

If the data is not linearly separable in the input space, then transformations $\phi(x)$ can be applied to the input data which map the data from the input space into a higher dimensional feature space [25]. And then apply the standard SVR algorithm. Because the SVR algorithm only depends on dot products between x_i , instead of applying $\phi(x)$ explicitly the mapping can be done implicitly via a kernel function.

The radial basis function (RBF) kernel is used in this work due to its efficiency to

compute and because a single parameter needs to be determined.

Evaluation metrics

The performance estimation of the forecasting model is essential for evaluating the accuracy of the designed models. The commonly used evaluation tools in the literature include mean absolute error (MAE), MAPE and root mean square error (RMSE). In this research study, MAPE has been used for evaluating the model performance because it allows finely comparing and interpreting the distinct results obtained with different model structures and configurations. MAPE evaluates uniform forecast error in percentage [26]:

$$MAPE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{|y_j - t_j|}{y_j} \times 100[\%] \quad (2)$$

Forecasters design

This section explains how the above-mentioned methodology has been applied to design and tune the three different forecasters. A previous correlation analysis has been performed so to see the linear correlation between the inputs and the consumption.

Inputs selection

Correlation study

Pearson coefficient has been used in order to analyse which are the inputs that most influence ESTIA 2 power consumption. In Figure 6, the dispersion of calculated coefficients values is shown for each season and some variable. The dispersion related to the R is not included but is very similar to that related to the OCC input, as expected.

The linear correlation between OCC and P_b in both seasons and between T_a and P_b in summer can clearly be seen. Regarding the correlation between P_b and T_a in winter, at first sight, it seems weak. That is because the consumption curve during the day has high variations, especially in winter, while the temperature in this season is rather stable during the whole day. Anyway, a correlation study made during the entire month of February between the maximum daily value T_a and the daily average value of P_b leads to a Pearson coefficient of $r = -0,586$. This result shows that effectively there is a global correlation between both variables.

Figure 6. Pearson correlation coefficient between different variables and seasons

As this study has not given definitive conclusions on the choice of inputs, in a second phase the MAPE obtained by each type of forecaster set with default parameters values and with different combinations of inputs are analysed.

Performance comparison for different input combinations

Among the different combinations of inputs, the main interest has been to compare the efficiency of the forecasters obtained with, on the one hand, the *bin* signal and, on the other hand, the *OCC* curve. The results of this study are given in Table 1. T_a has been taken as input in both cases (*bin* and *OCC*). In this analysis, a time window (TW) of 14 days has been considered. Moreover, default values have been assigned to the three forecasters' parameters.

Table 1 shows the performances obtained with the three different types of forecasters in winter (February) and summer (September) for the two options mentioned above. The forecasting accuracy achieved with workday occupancy data is much better than the one obtained with binary array, regardless of the type of model used.

Table 1. Comparison between input combinations with three prediction models (with models default parameters)

	Input combinations	Time Window	MAPE Winter			MAPE Summer		
			NARX	LSTM	SVR	NARX	LSTM	SVR
Block 1	Temperature + Binary Array	14 days	25.6	31.4	20.08	21.7	25.84	17.19
	Temperature + Occupancy	14 days	18.3	19.58	20.00	13.9	13.58	15.19

For the other two inputs, T_a and R , the results obtained with different combinations of inputs show that T_a is the most influential variable, and that R is the variable that least affects consumption. Therefore, in the following sections, *OCC* and T_a are considered as inputs of the three types of forecasting models.

Models hyperparameters adjustment

Nonlinear Autoregressive Exogenous Neural Network

Regarding NARX model, two different hyperparameters have been adjusted in order to obtain the lowest MAPE: i) the input and feedback delays and ii) the number of neurons in the single hidden layer. Delays have been tuned first. No significant variations have been noticed in the accuracy of the model when fixing different delays. Hence, the inputs and feedback delays have been fixed at their default value, 2.

Table 2 shows the MAPE obtained with different TW and neuron numbers has been included.

Table 2. MAPE results obtained with NARX combining different TW and number of neurons in the hidden layer

Input combinations	Time Window	N° Neurons	NARX MAPE	
			Winter	Summer
Block 2.1 Temperature + Occupancy	7 days	2	21,3	17,6
	7 days	3	19,65	16,4
	7 days	4	23,1	16,75
	7 days	5	19,4	14,3
	7 days	10	19,86	42,45
	14 days	2	18,25	14,6
	14 days	3	21,5	14,3
	14 days	4	18,9	15,15
	14 days	5	14,0	14,7
	14 days	10	16,60	14,71
	21 days	2	18,55	15,2
	21 days	3	16,0	12,3
	21 days	4	15,2	15,35
	21 days	5	14,9	13,0
	21 days	10	15,69	15,52
	28 days	2	17,0	12,4
	28 days	3	15,4	14,5
	28 days	4	15,3	14,9
	28 days	5	14,7	14,2
	28 days	10	14,59	14,97

A general conclusion can be underlined: regardless of the used TW, the best results are obtained with 5 neurons. So, as far as its structure is concerned, NARX network is set with a fixed delay of 2 steps and has 5 neurons in its single hidden layer. In all cases, *Levenberg-Marquardt* algorithm has been used as learning algorithm.

Long Short-Term Neural Network

Concerning LSTM model, a similar adjustment has been performed. Two hyperparameters have been tuned, namely, learning rate and number of neurons in the single hidden layer considered. First, the learning rate parameter has been adjusted. Different values ranges (1, 0.1, 0.01, 0.001, 0.0001 and 0.00001) have been considered in order to achieve the lowest MAPE. The lowest value has been obtained with a learning rate of 0.1. Therefore, the adjustment of the number of neurons has been performed with this value.

The MAPE values obtained with different TW and number of neurons has been gathered in Table 3. Winter results show that the most appropriate number of neurons is 15, as the lowest MAPE (around 19%) is obtained for the three largest TW ranges. Regarding the summer season, the values remain fairly constant for the range of the analysed neurons number (MAPE around 14%).

Table 3. MAPE results obtained with LSTM model combining different TW and number of neurons

Input combinations	Time Window	N° Neurons	LSTM MAPE	
			Winter	Summer
Temperature +	7 days	2	23,99	16,81

Occupancy	7 days	3	24,1	17,14
	7 days	4	24,15	16,97
	7 days	5	23,65	17,03
	7 days	10	23,89	16,92
	7 days	15	24,19	17,02
	7 days	20	24,01	17,05
	7 days	50	24,1	17,22
	14 days	2	23,72	14,84
	14 days	3	23,31	14,94
	14 days	4	23,44	15,24
	14 days	5	23,36	15,05
	14 days	10	22,65	14,79
	14 days	15	22,16	15,21
	14 days	20	22,18	14,99
	14 days	50	23,25	15,75
	21 days	2	19,38	14,82
	21 days	3	19,76	14,91
	21 days	4	19,63	14,13
	21 days	5	20,23	14,7
	21 days	10	19,79	14,85
	21 days	15	18,85	14,63
	21 days	20	19,46	14,54
	21 days	50	20,34	15,09
	28 days	2	21,14	13,84
	28 days	3	20,61	13,79
	28 days	4	21,02	13,73
	28 days	5	20,96	13,65
	28 days	10	21,03	13,73
28 days	15	19,99	13,67	
28 days	20	20,64	13,6	
28 days	50	21,07	14,03	

Summarising, a learning rate of 0.1 and 15 neurons have been selected to perform the forecast of the consumption with LSTM model. It has to be mentioned that epochs have been fixed with a validation rate of 6 steps and that *adam* algorithm has been used as learning algorithm.

Super Vector Regression

For SVR with a radial basis kernel, two hyperparameters need to be determined: C and the parameter γ of the RBF.

In our case the search range of the penalty coefficient C is set to $[10^{-6}, 10^2]$, as propose in [25]. The search range of γ is the same as that of the penalty coefficient C .

Each combination of model hyperparameters (C and γ) constitutes a model configuration. The model selection is carried out by estimating the performance of different model configurations to choose the best one. For that, the hyperparameters have been tuned using Bayesian optimization [27] and time-sensitive cross validation. To sum up, better accuracy is obtained when larger TWs are applied, in this case, with a TW of 21 and 28 days.

Table 4. MAPE results obtained with SVR combining different TW

Input combinations	Time Window	Winter			Summer		
		C	γ	SVR MAPE	C	γ	SVR MAPE

Block 2.3	Temperature +	7 days	0.040	1.1587	19.25	56.9375	0.0029	16.14
		14 days	0.4945	0.7109	20.00	0.7314	1.7969	15.29
	Occupancy	21 days	14.4654	0.0600	17.19	3.9961	2.0133	14.24
		28 days	3.0190	0.0268	18.21	100	0.0090	12.95

Time Window selection

Figure 7 summarises each forecaster performance for different TW in February and September months. In almost all cases, a significant improvement can be observed when moving from 7-days TW to 14-days TW. Similarly, better MAPE are obtained in five out of six cases when moving from 14-days TW to 21-days TW, in contrast to the case when moving to 28-days TW. Therefore, as the objective of this analysis is to choose the best overall TW for all model types, in order to make a rigorous comparison between them, a TW of 21-days is finally retained.

Figure 7. MAPE values of the three models for different TWs in February and September.

Results and discussion

This section presents the results obtained using the three designed and tuned forecast models. It is divided into two subsections in order to analyse the behaviour of the models separately in winter and summer.

Winter season results

Table 5 presents the MAPE calculated by averaging for each day of the week in February. Results show how NARX model performs better than LSTM and SVR models. Average MAPE obtained in February by each forecasters is 13.98% with NARX, 18.31% with LSTM and 16.96% with SVR. MAPE differences could be explained by the fact that LSTM models are more suitable for large training data sets. As far as SVR is concerned, the lack of a recurrent term may explain the poorer results obtained.

As mentioned before, the HVAC system, which is the most energy-consuming device in ESTIA 2, has a stochastic behaviour. This may explain why the best MAPEs are obtained on weekends and especially on Sundays, when most units of the HVAC system are not operating.

Table 5. MAPE mean values of each day of the week, in winter season.

WINTER	MAPE NARX	MAPE LSTM	MAPE SVR
Monday	13.52	18.12	15,30
Tuesday	14.76	24.37	19,03
Wednesday	14.21	22.25	17,64
Thursday	15.45	23.37	16,30
Friday	13.08	19.64	14,65
Saturday	15.63	18.25	23,77
Sunday	12.32	13.43	11,98

Figure 8 shows the forecasts obtained by each type of model during the week of 17th of February. It can be observed that the predictors are able to detect both the trend over a full day and the difference between workdays and weekends. The worst results are obtained when consecutive abrupt changes in power consumption occur, especially during the night. These sudden night-time variations could be explained by the on/off behaviour of HVAC units in operation with constant set points but large hysteresis.

Regarding the comparison of the behaviour of the three types of models, it seems that the SVR model has difficulties in reaching the consumption peaks when important consumption curve changes occur between two consecutive days (from Sunday to Monday and from Friday to Saturday). With regard to the NARX and LSTM models, they both show a similar behaviour (see Figure 4). It is necessary to underline that the best prediction results with both models have been obtained during working days, being this important because it will be the weekday prediction that will be taken into account in the EMS.

Figure 8. Consumption forecast of a week for winter season.

Summer season results

Table 6 shows the MAPE calculated by averaging for each day of the week in September. In this case, as before, NARX model performs the best prediction, with an average MAPE of 12.08%, while the average MAPE of the LSTM model is 14.49% and that of the SVR model is 14.43%.

Compared to the MAPE values obtained in winter, the improved results during the summer month can be explained by the reduced use of the HVAC system. Indeed, in September, external temperatures are more moderate and there is less need to heat or cool the building. This fact is very interesting, since the summer season is when there is usually more PV production, and therefore, the EMS will be more efficient in increasing the ratio of self-consumed energy.

Table 6. MAPE mean values of each day of the week, in summer season.

SUMMER	MAPE NARX	MAPE LSTM	MAPE SVR
Monday	15.36	16.27	17,81
Tuesday	17.92	13.25	13,34
Wednesday	16.38	13.94	9,76
Thursday	9.54	10.82	12,01
Friday	10.54	9.70	11,82
Saturday	8.62	12.51	15,15
Sunday	5.67	16.40	21,14

As it can be seen in Figure 9, the reduced use of the HVAC system mentioned above clearly influences the consumption curve, leading to a decrease in the amplitude of the saw-tooth behaviour. Moreover, since the shape of the curve is cleaner, the prediction by the three models is better. Here, as in winter, models are able to distinguish day and night, as well as working days and weekends. The most important error seems to be related to the difficulties in reaching the consumption peaks measured during the week. This could be associated to a different occupancy behaviour of the users in September.

Figure 9. Consumption forecast of a week for summer season.

Conclusions

In this work, NARX, LSTM and SVR machine learning techniques have been used to predict ESTIA 2 building power consumption for the next 24 h with a small set of data.

The first conclusion that can be drawn is that, in the considered framework, the highest accuracy is obtained with the NARX model in both, winter and summer seasons, obtaining a MAPE of 13.98% and 12.08% respectively. The global average is therefore a MAPE of 13.03%. Thus, in this case study, the NARX model performs 26% better than the LSTM model and 21% better than the SVR model.

Regardless of the used technique, the prediction of consumption in the summer month is achieved with a higher accuracy. In the case of LSTM model for example, the MAPE in winter is more than 5% higher than in summer. This is related to the fact that the building HVAC system, which as mentioned above has a stochastic behaviour, is much less used in September than in February. In the latest version of the EMS, it is planned to forecast the consumption of ESTIA 2 without taking into account the consumption of heat pumps. In this way, the flexibility related to the energy consumption of the HVAC system would be used without affecting the consumption trend to be forecasted. Therefore, the forecast of this EMS should perform better.

Likewise, when analysing the structure of the models, it is worth highlighting the importance of the input choice and their combination for acceptable prediction. A very substantial improvement has been achieved by introducing, together with the temperature, the occupancy rate of the building instead of the binary array that distinguished only workdays and weekends/holidays.

The next steps of this research study will be to implement the NARX prediction model in the EMS that operates in real-time for the PV energy CSC in Izarbel technological park. For that, predicted temperature data will be used instead of historical measured data. Moreover, considering that in France the self-consumption repartition is measured each 30 minutes, the consumption will be predicted for each half an hour. Furthermore, the predictions will be updated each step time with updated input data.

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